

The Holy Apostles Community, Ayetoro

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Aladura, The Holy Apostles Community, Ayetoro

The Holy Apostles Community, Ayetoro was founded in January 1947. The community came into existence after an irreconcilable difference broke between the Holy Apostles and the traditional institution in Ilajeland. The former had strongly opposed and publicly condemned the traditional practice of twin infanticide sanctioned by the latter in their homeland at the time. Prior to these confrontations, members of the Ayetoro community had identified as followers of the Cherubim and Seraphim Society which was introduced to Ilajeland in 1929. They had accused the leadership of the Cherubim and Seraphim in Ilajeland of acquiescence with the traditional practice and warned that the society would lose its relevance if it failed to speak up against the practice. Several acts of civil disobedience were reported against the prophets and members of the group which would later adopt the name: Holy Apostles. Some of them were fined by the local authority while others served jail terms over charges preferred against them by the traditional institution which they contended with. But these punitive measures were not able to break their ranks until they organised themselves and began to migrate to uninhabited islands and swamps which belonged to families of notable personalities among them. Their first attempt at establishing a theocratic community was made in 1945. The primary aim of the group was to organise themselves and establish a new community which would be free from the influence and control of the local authority in their homeland. This attempt failed owing to the report made against the Holy Apostles by the traditional institution they opposed. Upon the receipt of the report, the District Officer at the Okitipupa Divisional Office of the Colonial Administration came down to the newly founded community to investigate the report. A member of the community attempted to harm the District Officer who brought the full weight of the law on the leaders of the newly founded community. When he and others arrested with him were released from custody, he refused to return to the community. This left a leadership gap which had to be filled. There were fears of attacks and mass arrests from the authorities. This informed the new leader's consultations with the members on the need to relocate to a new site. They therefore migrated to Ayetoro in January 1947. In 1948, the Oba (monarch) of Ayetoro introduced communalism to the community. All members relinquished ownership of their personal belongings to the community and a new wave of development was witnessed. Within a decade, Ayetoro had become the first community to have public electricity in the Old Ondo Area. Besides, the community had built a functional technical workshop and college which trained marine engineers and other categories of technicians. They built a primary school and the first secondary school in Ilajeland. They invested heavily in transportation business by building boats which aided the movement of persons, goods and services along the waterways between Lagos in the west and Cameroon in the east. The community built fishing trawlers which launched into the ocean, harvesting varieties of fish which the community sold in markets locally and in Lagos. They built modern houses and constructed solid walkways on stilts. This development aided movement across the entire community and supported the Oba's car to tour the community. It was a novel invention in Ilajeland. The community's economic and technological advancement was rapid and well sustained that it soon began to attract the attention of the government and global development bodies. By 1970, Ayetoro abolished communalism and it soon began to witness decay to its economic assets. Today, the only visible traces of the once prosperous community are the relics of the assets it once deployed for economic and technological development. Over the years, Ayetoro has gone through some stages in her spiritual journey. In the past, especially at some point during the period of its massive economic and technological drive it played down on religion. It has again witnessed a revival of its spiritual fervour. The continuous existence of the community is threatened owing to the massive ocean surge which has permanently swept more than half of its original landmass under the Atlantic Ocean.

Date Range: 1947 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Aiyetoro, Ilajeland, Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria

Aiyetoro is a faith settlement established by a group of devote Christians who had been forced out of their natal settlements owing to the irreconcilable difference between them and the local authority in their homeland. In 1948, a year after its establishment, the community decided to practice communalism. Although their practice of communalism lasted only about two decades, the community witnessed unprecedented economic and technological advancement during this time. The community has since adopted a free economy and being faced with ecological threats to its existence, it has continued to hold on to the faith upon which it was founded.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Barrett, R. Stanley, *The Rise and Fall of an African Utopia: A Wealthy Theocracy in Comparative Perspective* (Ontario: Wilfrid Laurier University Press, 1977)
- Source 2: Barrett, R. Stanley, *Two Villages on Stilts: Economic and Family Change in Nigeria* (New York: Chandler Publishing Company, 1974)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Aiyetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.africanportal.net/ABO/BibeliAtoka/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Aiyetoro, Southwest Nigeria

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Notes: For more than two decades after the founding of Ayetoro, the community had no positive cultural contact with other religious groups in their area. Since the community was founded as a protest movement against the traditional institution in their homeland, it was breathing under heavy sanctions and opposition from this established institution. Furthermore, they had criticised the popular religious movement (The Cherubim and Seraphim Society) they previously belonged for not speaking against the practice they considered inconsistent with their faith. They had renounced their membership of the group before going ahead to establish their own faith settlement. This left them with no friends or allies in their immediate environment. They survived on their own and had to build their community completely without the assistance or help of their neighbours. No religious group was willing to associate with them. The situation only changed around 1970 when the king (the third ruler) attempted to adopt branches for Ayetoro. A few religious communities in their area indicated interest in forming solid relationship with Ayetoro but the attempt failed to yield any lasting result. However, from 1970 the community has become open to forming friendships with other religious communities around them. Months ago, the Oba (king) of Ayetoro was the special guest at the Annual Convention of Ugbonla, a Cherubim and Seraphim theocratic community near Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The Holy Apostles Community of Ayetoro does not engage in a competitive cultural contact with any religious group in her neighbourhood. Proselyting has never been part of the community's expansionary drive. Besides, the community was drawn in a very deep moral conflict with the local authority in their homeland in the events leading to the establishment of their community. This was the primary reason why the people migrated to an uninhabited island separate and outside of the control of the traditional institution which governed their region. As such, they lived in the midst of hostile neighbours who did not want to have anything to do with them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact Ayetoro had with her neighbours from its founding to about 1970 was neither accommodating nor pluralistic. At that time, Ayetoro was a closed community. They lived among hostile neighbours. They also did not want to have much to do with their neighbours given the dynamics of the relationship. Though their initial attempts to become more open to interactions was largely unsuccessful, in recent times however, the situation has began to change but still needs to be further strengthened.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: In time past, Ayetoro lived among hostile neighbours. They equally did not want to get involved with their neighbours. The suspicion and distrust between Ayetoro and her neighbours was mutual. Though the era of suspicion is gone, the past is still not completely behind them. There has been some positive interaction between Ayetoro and their neighbours in recent past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There is a history of violent conflict preceding the formation of Ayetoro. The frosty relationship between Ayetoro and her neighbours continued for at least two decades after its founding. However, the situation has changed as violent conflicts have ceased between Ayetoro and her neighbours.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There is no record of violent conflicts between Ayetoro and groups outside the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Membership is conferred on children born to parents who identify as members of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Adults, in the exercise of their freedom of association are granted membership upon the indication of interest to become charter members of Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There are no class barriers placed on people willing to join the Ayetoro religious community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no discrimination on the basis age for individuals willing to join the Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: There is no gender discrimination for those willing to become members of the Ayetoro community. Men as well as women are free to become members of the Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: No ritual obligation is required of intending members of Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: No extraneous factors are to be met by individuals willing to join the Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not actively proselytize neither does the community engage in active membership recruitment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The religious group has never had any official political support

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: in 1948, a year after the founding of Ayetoro, the community decided to practice communalism. All personal property were handed over to the community following which every member submitted themselves (their time and energy) to the control of the community. The members were assigned to participate in various economic activities while the income derived from their labours went to a central purse under the control of the Oba (king). The people worked in groups. Given the frosty relationship between the community and their neighbours, members of Ayetoro community were disallowed contact with their families outside the village while the significance of family bonding in the community was downplayed for the collective spirit of the brotherhood. However, some members found the situation in Ayetoro too strenuous to bear. Such individuals stole away under the cover of the night or at some other times when they would not be spotted. Such actions were considered abominable in the community. The individuals who had returned to their natal settlements were considered to be apostates.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Apostates in Ayetoro were not punished because the only way they became apostates was by fleeing the village. Because they were never apprehended in the process of fleeing, there was no way of prosecuting or punishing them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000

Notes: About 2000 people joined Ayetoro in 1947 but a year later, due to abscondment, only about half the original population remained in the community (Barrett, 1974, p. 7). However, the 1991 National census puts Ayetoro population at 14,521. By this figures, the community's population was the highest among the nearly fifty religious (theocratic) communities in Ilajeland. It also ranked among the five most populous among the 177 communities in the entire Ilajeland. Though Ayetoro still has a vibrant population, it is currently besieged by perennial ocean surge which has claimed about half of the community's land mass.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 28.93

Notes: Nigeria's National Population commission put Ayetoro's population at 14,521 in 1991 while the Ilaje region where Ayetoro is located was said to have 50188 inhabitants from the census report. This leave Ayetoro with 28.93% of Ilaje's total population as at 1991. There has been only one other census conducted in 2006. However, its figures were disputed across a section of the nation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Notes: Ayetoro has been a significant religious group in Ilajeland. From its establishment in 1947 to 1970. During this time, it was a closed community and was intolerant of affiliations from other smaller religious groups in its environment. The third Oba however tried making some other theocratic communities branches of Ayetoro around 1970. This attempt failed to yield the anticipated result. After this event, the community has become open and accessible but no successful affiliations have been recorded with other religious (theocratic) communities around it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The Oba is the recognised leader of Ayetoro. He is both the spiritual as well as the secular leader of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Ayeetoro is a religious community which has its supreme leader in the Oba. The Oba is at the apex of the leadership structure in the community. No other individual measures to his position either within or outside the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: From about 1947 to 1970, Ayetoro was a closed community. It had very little to do with other communities around it. Because the community achieved a significant level of economic and technological advancement above her immediate neighbours, there were instances when their neighbours had to relate with them. These relationships were basically business related. Their neighbours were compelled to either buy goods (like household needs) from Ayetoro or obtain expertise or education from their technical or secondary school. Such relationships did not, however erode the strain in their relationship. It was only after 1970 that Ayetoro attempted to extend her dominance in Ilajeland. Ayetoro extended invitation to other theocratic settlements in the area to come under its control for the purpose of economic and technological advancement of those settlements. This did not yield fruits before such affiliations were called off. In effect, Ayetoro does not have functional branches. Her Oba is not a regional leader who oversees one or more local leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: The authority of the Oba of Ayetoro is exercised exclusively within the community. He only oversees other leaders within his community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: The council of elders in Ayetoro sit over matters that concern the community. Their jurisdiction does not extend beyond the community as they do not have other religious groups which fall under the control of the community. Their resolutions could be reviewed by the Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: Every member of Ayetoro has basic rights within the community. Citizenship is recognised and is the basic level of authority anyone can lay claims to in the community. The next level of hierarchy is that of the youth leadership. If there is any issue that requires adjudication, settlement or intervention, the youth leaders make attempts at resolving them. If this is unsuccessful, the Council of Elders step in. If parties are still not satisfied, the Oba has the final authority to decide on or adjudicate over such cases. Every matter is laid to rest once the Oba intervenes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders in Ayetoro are believed to possess supernatural powers. These powers are believed to have been released to them by God and is for the benefit of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not project or hold the notion that power is acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: The notion of the acquisition of power by individuals due to deeds they carried out in current is somewhat true in Ayetoro. However, such deeds must have been carried out in obedience to the supernatural being. Prophets in Ayetoro are perceived

as individuals who are sold out and have been consistent with their life of devotion to God. As they relate to God and become vessels for carrying out divine mandate, their propensity for greater works increase. This consistency in their usefulness for divine purpose can earn them powers for higher responsibilities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: Powers are not inherited in Ayetoro. Of all the seven Obas (Ogeloyinbo) who have reigned in Ayetoro, only the current Oba is the direct grandson of the first leader. All other leaders have come from different families or even nativities. Even though the current oba is the grandson of the first leader of the community, his emergence was characterised by a long drawn disagreement between him and a somewhat more powerful candidate to the throne. He was for sometime incarcerated but the huge support of his candidature from the community turned events in his favour.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: At the death of an Oba, the leading prophet in the community has significant influence in deciding who emerges as the next leader. Such roles are still subject to some other considerations. The youths, elders and indeed the whole community must be swayed in favour of an individual to validate their aspiration to the throne. The spiritual prowess of each candidate to the throne usually constitutes a deciding factor for the community members. Power, therefore, cannot fully said to be culturally transmitted from a supernatural being in Ayetoro as human factors have proven to be equally important in the selection process of the Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: No human is in the position to singlehandedly decide who leads Ayetoro as Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Each leadership position in Ayetoro has its unique responsibilities. The office of the Oba being the highest in Ayetoro has powers associated to it and only the

occupant of that office is empowered to perform the functions of the office.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders in Ayetoro are chosen. Although the first Oba of the community who led the first settlers into the territory emerged by his charismatic tendencies and not necessarily by consensus. His emergence was not objected to by the majority of the people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: A leader does not choose their replacement in Ayetoro. The process for selecting a new Oba usually commences after the death of the Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: The process for the selection of an Oba in Ayetoro is not determined by the ministers of the leader. The council of elders is somewhat independent and expected to discharge their responsibility in the overriding interest of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: No political leader has a duty to perform in the emergence of the leader of Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: The leading prophet in Ayetoro at the time of the death of an Oba has a role to play in the emergence of a new leader. The prophet is believed to seek guidance of the supernatural being but he does this in conjunction with the council of elders as well as

the representatives of the youths. The process is conducted collaboratively which ensures the popularity of anyone who emerges as the Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro has no branches in the sample region. The community organises its internal affairs including the emergence of a new leader. Representatives of the different groups (youths, women and elders) work collaboratively towards the decision on the choice of a new Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro people believe in consultations with supernatural powers in choosing a new Oba.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders are considered fallible in Ayetoro. Leaders themselves have had to review some of their previous decisions. This confirms their fallibility.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Members of the Ayetoro community hardly speak about the fallibility of a popular Oba. However, historically, they have rejected vehemently the imposition of unpopular candidates to the throne.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There have been reports of discontentment by some popular prophets who had an eye on the throne. Few of the prophets acclaimed to have such ambitions pulled out of the community to start a new religious community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the intractable cultural differences which led to the emergence of Ayetoro when the twin infanticide promoted by the traditional institution was rejected by its members, no serious charges of fallibility have been made by political leaders against the Oba or leadership of Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Close followers and disciples of religious leaders in Ayetoro are always unquestionably obedient to and accept the leader's pronouncement on all matters.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes in the sanctity of the Holy Bible and admonishes members to follow its injunctions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the high god revealed his word to prophets of old and specifically instructed some of them to document the encounters with him

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: There are occasions when other supernatural beings take part in events that are recorded in the bible. When this takes place, the supernatural beings involved in the process are doing so as representatives of the high god and not in their own powers or authority.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: It is the universal belief of the community that scriptures are inspired to man by the high god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: The notion of divine or semi-divine human beings does not exist in Ayetoro. As a result, divine or semi-divine human beings are not held as originators of their scriptures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Though their scriptures are not alterable, there had been reports in the past when a certain Oba claimed there would not have been a need to read the bible or hold church meetings if all the members were behaving well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: No institutions exist for the purpose of interpreting the scriptures. The community beliefs in the inspiration of the holy spirit (the spirit of their high god) for interpreting the scriptures to their religious leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The community does not transmit their scriptures (bibles) as such spiritual materials are obtained from the market.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The bible is in use in Ayetoro. The bible has been canonised and codified by church

authorities centuries ago and a consensus exists differently among the Roman Catholics and the protestants on the books in their different versions of the bible. Ayetoro community beliefs in the bible with 66 canonised books.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 2

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 800

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 18

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 2

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 1.5

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 2

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: No marked tomb is ever found in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: There is no cemetery in Ayetoro. Corpses are buried in unmarked tombs and the location of their burial place remains unknown not only to outsiders but to many members who are not involved in burial activities in the community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community has only one church. This is the community church where all members of the community are expected to worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: The community church has an altar where the Oba sits and from where he preaches to the congregation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The community church is an essential devotional marker in Ayetoro. Prayer garments have also become prominent in Ayetoro religious life. Some prophets in the community have also been identified with short staff as an instrument of office and for undertaking spiritual tasks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The community church and the community hall are two important gathering points in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: There is a very heavy bell imported into Ayetoro community from Holland which served the purpose of alerting members to keep in mind the time of church services in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Iconography isn't popular in Ayetoro spiritual life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The church is the only known sacred site in Ayetoro community. However, when the community experienced some crisis and members were prevented from accessing the church, religious meetings were moved to the community hall and some other places pending the resolution of the crisis

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages are not so popular among the people of Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-body distinction is present in Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts. The departure of the spirit-mind from the human body spells death and the end of the earthly existence of any human.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the spirit-mind is non-material and ontologically distinct from the body. Although they go further to hold it as an important component and the real essence of the human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Notes: There are no other distinctions between the spirit and body apart from the fact that they are key components of the human essence. Though the spirit sustains the body, the body perishes after the spirit is departed from it. The spirit however outlives the body but in another realm of existence in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro theocratic community believes in the afterlife. The community believes that those who lived a good life would be translated to a blissful habitation after their earthly existence while those whose have done evil during their earthly existence who be punished for their wrongs in a place of torment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not belief in reincarnation in this world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: No information is available in the public sphere on the treatment of corpses in Ayetoro. In the early days of Ayetoro, the inevitability of death was denied. When a few members died during this period, the community rationalised the cause of their death. They were held as people who sinned (committed infractions against the principles of the community or partook of evil acts) and were punished by the supernatural being. This policy changed when death increased due to an aging population and sickness. However, no ceremonies are held for the dead neither does the community have marked graves for the dead. Burials are usually carried out under the cover of the night. No member of the community is knowledgeable about the subject while the participants in the event are not easily identified nor are willing to make statements about the practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not present in Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: No formal burials are present in Ayetoro neither does the community have marked graves for their departed ones. Burials are executed in the night while members of the community are generally oblivion on the practice. Those saddled with the responsibility are not easily known and are often unwilling to make answer questions about the practice

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro beliefs in the existence of supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community attributes human traits, emotions, or intentions to the supreme high god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community hold that the supreme high god is a sky deity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community hold that the supreme high god is a sky deity and not a chthonic deity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The supreme high god in Ayetoro is not fused with their monarch. The high god is superior to the monarch

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community accepts that all mortals, including their monarch emanate from the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not accept that the supreme high god is a kin relation to elites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not accept that the supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community hold that the supreme high god is unquestionably good. He is not capable of evil in any guise.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: In Ayetoro, the supreme high god is reputed to possess all good attributes. He is all good, all knowing, all powerful, merciful, gracious etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme god's knowledge is not restricted to particular domain of human affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not hold the view that the high god's knowledge is restricted to specific areas within the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted both within and outside the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted both within and outside the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the supreme high god can see humans everywhere normally visible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, it is believed that the supreme high god can see humans everywhere normally visible in the dark or at home.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, it is believed that the supreme high god can see the heart/mind of humans including their hidden motives

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, it is believed that the supreme high god knows the basic character or personal essence of all humans

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that the supreme high god is all knowing. He knows what will happen to all humans in the future

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god has other knowledge of this world. He is believed to be in control of the universe and orders the course of every event therein.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that the supreme high god can reward every good action among humans. He either directly or indirectly orders a just and appropriate reward for the actions of every member of the human race.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that the supreme high god can punish every wrong action among humans. He either directly or indirectly orders a just and appropriate punishment for the deliberate wrong actions of every member of the human race.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro religious community holds that the supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world. The pervading philosophy in the community supports the position that the supreme high god gives humans the freedom to make choices. Once a human then makes his choices the effect of such actions are beyond the decision of the one who took them. They hold the position that the supreme high god supports the law of karma.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community hold that the supreme high god exhibits positive emotion. Such positive emotions they hold the supreme high god possible of exhibiting include kindness, mercy, favour and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community belief that the supreme high god exhibits negative emotions which includes vengeance and anger.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not hold the view that the supreme high god is capable of hunger for food. Their high god, according to them does not derive sustenance or nourishment from food. If at all some form of hunger is associated with their god, it is the hunger for reward for good and commendable actions and the hunger for punishment for negative actions etc. His hunger is for maintaining order and

a just recompense for the deeds of every mortal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not worship other supernatural beings apart from the high god. It is not permissible for anyone among them to worship any other supernatural being other than the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Ayetoro community holds the conviction that the supreme high god possesses and exhibits an endless list of good and infinitely positive features. Some of those other features attributed to their supreme high god among them include peace, graciousness, protection, love and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ayetoro community, the supreme high god communicates with the living in their everyday activity. However, the ability to feel the presence of the supreme high god is dependent on the capacity of individuals to draw close and remain in close relationship with their god. Because of their towering image in religious sphere in Ayetoro, prophets are considered as having a greater capacity to recognise when the supreme high god is communicating with them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god communicates

with them in dreams. Their prophets are acclaimed to have a greater capacity to feel the presence of the supreme high god in their dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god communicates with them in trance possession. Their prophets are acclaimed to have a greater capacity to feel the presence of the supreme high god in trance possession.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god communicates with them through their divination practice. Their method of divining is through prayers. Every member of the community has the privilege to approach their supreme high god through divination (prayers). However, their prophets are acclaimed to have a greater capacity to feel the presence of the supreme high god and understand the feelings, instructions and solutions proffered to the challenges they present to him while divining and interacting with their god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: In Ayetoro, all members of the community have access to the supreme high god. They can all approach him in prayers and supplications and so many of them do approach the high god for their personal concerns. However, their religious specialists (prophets) are reputed to have a higher degree of success when communicating with the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Only through monarch

– No

Notes: In Ayetoro, all members of the community have access to the supreme high god. They can all approach him in prayers and supplications and so many of them do approach the high god for their personal concerns. However, their monarch who is also the leader of their religious specialists (prophets) is

reputed to have a higher degree of success when communicating with the supreme high god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Ayetoro community holds that the supreme high god reaches out to them through circumstances, through the reading of the scriptures, through prophecies etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not believe in that previous human spirits are present in their community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the presence of non-human supernatural beings is acknowledged.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings acknowledged in Ayetoro cannot be seen though their powers and presence are widely proclaimed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The presence of the supernatural beings cannot be physically felt though their existence, place and significance is widely acknowledged.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings acknowledged in Ayetoro are not restricted to particular domain of human affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of non-human supernatural beings acknowledged in Ayetoro is not restricted to a specific area within the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge of non-human supernatural beings acknowledged in Ayetoro is not restricted within the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere normally visible (in public)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere (in the dark, at home)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see hidden motives inside human hearts/minds

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings know the basic character or personal essence of humans

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to all mortals and what they will do in future

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: In Ayetoro, it is believed that non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro does not hold the view that non-human supernatural beings exist in the world

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not believe in the existence of mixed human-divine beings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The only supernatural being Ayetoro community recognises is the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that supernatural monitoring is present among them. Their supreme high god is reputed to be involved in active monitoring all human activities and actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro beliefs that there is a constant supernatural monitoring of prosocial norms exhibited by all humans everywhere. Their supreme high god monitors the adherence to

prosocial norms also actively monitors antisocial activities everywhere. They also hold that the supreme high god metes out appropriate rewards and sanctions for adherence and disobedience to societal norms regulations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: There are no known food taboos instituted in Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Sacred spaces are not to be desecrated in Ayetoro. All sacred spaces are to be treated in accordance with their status.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Sacred objects are not to be desecrated in Ayetoro. All sacred objects are to be treated in accordance with their status. Sacred objects which include religious garments and paraphernalia of office of religious specialists are to be held and treated as their status dictates.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: According to Ayetoro community, the supernatural being cares about the work ethics of the people. Being a highly economically viable and productive community, the people hold the view that laziness is unacceptable to their high god. The high god also demands truthfulness from the people at all times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of coreligionists is not permitted in Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any member of the human race is unacceptable by Ayetoro community. They hold that their supreme high god would require the blood of every mortal from the hands of whosoever causes their death. However, they agree that under human regulations, governments could sanction the death of anyone found to be guilty of grievous crimes against humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities. They hold that there is no justification for taking the lives of any member of other polities under any guise.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is an antisocial activity in Ayetoro. It is not permitted and attracts sanctions in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, incest is not permitted in Ayetoro. It is unacceptable among the Yoruba ethnic group which the Ilaje subgroup which Ayetoro members are largely drawn from. However, it is reported that the idea was once muted by the third Oba but was largely unpopular and widely rejected by the members (Barrett, *Two Villages on Stilts*; 85, 94-95, 109).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: In the early days of the community, premarital sex was disallowed. However, there is less emphasis placed on the practice in recent times, especially when those involved in it have the plan to become couple in future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is frowned at and considered an antisocial act in Ayetoro because the supernatural beings disapprove of it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings care about honouring oaths in Ayetoro. The people hold that the supernatural beings themselves keep their oaths with the people and are therefore interested in Ayetoro members keeping their oaths and fulfilling them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro people cannot condone the laziness of any member. It is one of the significant practices the people frown at. In fact, from 1948 when Ayetoro adopted communalism, their economic and technological advancement was evident to the world. They could achieve this level of development because they were incurably productive. They worked seven days a week and diversified into various economic activities for the next two decades. Even when they took ill, it was important that they left the comfort of their homes and get involved in one communal or economic activity or the other in order to get better.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is an abomination in Ayetoro. Prior to the founding of Ayetoro in Ilajeland, the entire area was conceived to be under the control of evil supernatural forces. Sorcery was one of the activities associated with the evil folks. As a revolt to the pervading traditional practices in their land, Ayetoro frowned at sorcery and was keen about exposing witches and wizards who, according to them, found their way into the community. They believed that sorcery was responsible for the underdevelopment in other Ilaje communities and were poised to keep its influence away of their community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the supernatural beings frown at members engaged in non-lethal fighting. They dislike all forms of fights within or outside the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings with which the Ayetoro community identify do not shirk risk neither do they look kindly at their followers doing same. When a duty is handed to any of the followers in the community/church, it is done in the firm belief that the supernatural who is all knowing and all powerful has endowed the fellow with all powers and conditions necessary to fulfil the mandate. Hence, it brings disappointment to them when such task is evaded, avoided or haphazardly done

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Generally in Yorubaland, elders are expected to be accorded respect. The Ayetoro community peopled by a subgroup of the Yoruba race also hold that their supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders. In the administration of the community, the council of elders are quite prominent and visible in the public sphere. The current monarch of Ayetoro has instituted a social scheme which caters for the peculiar needs of elders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping is frowned at in Ayetoro. This is so because the supernatural beings which Ayetoro community follow abhors the practice as it divides rather than binds the people together.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the supernatural beings care about property crimes. As a result, no one in the community is permitted to engage in any crimes whatsoever. Although from 1948 to about 1970, no member of Ayetoro community held personal property owing to their practice of communalism, when the economic system was abolished in 1970, individuals were still discouraged from partaking in property crimes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals, by their very nature are expected to be carried out following a prescribed order and sequence of events. This is so with rituals in Ayetoro. They hold the view that supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance. No member of the community is permitted to be absent from religious meetings while members' participation in ritual observances is mandatory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings in Ayetoro care about performance of rituals. Ritual observances in Ayetoro grease the wheels which bind the community together. It is therefore mandatory for rituals to be carried out at the right time, in the right manner and following the correct order.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings in Ayetoro are interested in the conversion of non-religionists and their accommodation within the settlement. Because Ayetoro was a closed community, all non-religionists who accepted the community's way of life were required to relocate to the

village to begin a new life. Now that the community is open, members are free to relocate to the village or identify as members in the Diaspora while carrying on with their daily business.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the supernatural beings care about economic fairness. They do not hold kindly to sharp practices in trade and commerce involving Ayetoro members as every member of the community is expected to exhibit fairness in their economic activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community maintain good personal hygiene. They are often reminded of their duty of personal cleanness because it impacts the collective health of the community. After taking care of their personal hygiene, members of Ayetoro are often seen engaging in communal work like weeding their surrounding and cleaning other communal areas in a bid to remain healthy and safe of dangers associated with uncleanness

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: According to the reasoning of Ayetoro members, there are several other matters which the supernatural beings care about. These include the members safety from all forms of accident, their prosperity, their defence etc. It is widely acclaimed in Ayetoro that none of her members could be consumed in any form of accident. Reports are rife in Ayetoro of members' miraculous deliverance from auto crashes, fire incidents, boat mishaps and air crashes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, supernatural beings are conceived as the force controlling events. They ensure that every mortal gets a just recompense of their actions. Though they may not be directly or actively involved in this actions, they are held as the force that ensures the correct reward or punishment for every past deed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: While Ayetoro community agree that humans possess the freedom to act as they deem necessary, the consequences of their actions cannot be determined by them. They hold that agents of supernatural punishment are known but these agents are diverse. Evil forces, other humans and the good forces of the world are seen as agents of supernatural punishment by the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community hold that the high god is one of the agents of punishment. He could choose to mete out punishments by himself or use other agents to effect the same purpose.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community hold that the high god could choose to use many supernatural beings like angels to mete out punishments for wrongs done by humans. Other supernatural beings are agents in the hands of the high god to punish wrongs done by any mortal

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Just as the high god deploys other means to punish wrongdoing, there are times when impersonal cause-effect principles are used as tools for chastising members for wrongs done. This principle is not seen as mere coincidence in Ayetoro where the law of karma is held as a universal principle.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Evil forces are seen as tools for bringing punishment to errant members of Ayetoro community. In addition, destiny is also conceived as sacrosanct among the people. It is conceived that the destiny of any errant member is their ultimate

punishment for their disobedience. In this wise, destiny also serves the purpose of bringing a just recompense of past wrong doing among the people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In certain instances, reasons behind supernatural punishments may be easily explained while at other times, the reasons be left to the realm of conjectures. Many times, punishments are seen as tools deployed to deter people from future wrongdoing. Its enforcement could be retributive or to serve some other purposes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The enforcement of religious ritual-devotional adherence is one of the purposes punishments serve among the people of Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: When individuals pass through tough or difficult times in Ayetoro, questions could be asked around any anti-social acts they may have been involved in. If a group norm has been flouted by a member, such behaviour in disregard of group norms could be rationalised as grounds for their suffering or punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Punishments are seen as capable of inhibiting selfish tendencies among members of the Ayetoro community. The community holds that selfishness breaks the bond which should exist among members. They frown at the manifestation of selfishness among the people and are quick to include selfishness as one of the possible causes of punishments members may be suffering when probing the reasons behind their predicament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: In Ayetoro, punishment are not usually conceived as being meted out randomly. Punishments are seen as instruments of enforcing the law of karma. Whether in their private or public conversations, punishments are seen as just rewards for disobedience, disregard or neglect of social norms or religious injunctions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishments are seen in Ayetoro as instruments for enforcing social justice. They are also conceived as tools for enforcing compliance to social norms and group regulations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds that supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife. The mere thought of the inevitability punishments for wrong doing in the afterlife compels some to follow group norms and stick to regulations governing the conduct of members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized and meticulously taught. The community holds that there will be an eternal punishment which no wrongdoer can escape in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Mild sensory displeasure is a critical feature of the components of eternal punishments in the afterlife as conceived by the Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Extreme sensory displeasure is a critical feature of the components of eternal punishments in the afterlife as conceived by the Ayetoro community. They hold that people who will partake of the displeasures of hellfire or Hades in the afterlife will be subject to a variety chaotic and unsettling experiences including mild and extreme sensory displeasures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Ascribing an inferior form of existence to reincarnated humans in the afterlife as a form of punishment for their wrongdoing in the first (current) life is alien to Ayetoro belief system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Placing humans in an inferior realm of existence during reincarnation in the afterlife as a form of punishment for their wrongdoing in the first (current) life is alien to Ayetoro belief system. In fact, Ayetoro does not preach the doctrine of reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Strictly speaking, Ayetoro does not preach the doctrine of reincarnation. The community holds that though humans will drop their current body, they will take up a new body in the afterlife. The new body as well as the old are both capable of experiencing displeasure, discomfort and pain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that supernatural punishments begin from this lifetime. People who deserve punishments for their wrongdoing begin to have a taste of it here on earth then continue in the afterlife to receive an unending punishment for their unacceptable acts. The community believes that the most important justification for punishment in this life is for

those found to have done wrong to rethink their ways and change to doing what is right and acceptable. If they do amend their ways, the punishment has fulfilled its purpose. The supernatural being is most happy because the punishment has brought about the desired changes and saved a soul from eternal destruction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro religious community emphasises supernatural punishments in this life. They hold this view and justify the sanctity of their convictions by rationalising the cause of a member's misfortune as a supernatural punishment for a wrongdoing done in the past. It often happens that when a member of the community experiences a mishap, insinuations may be making the rounds that the fellow may be suffering from the consequences of their sins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds the view that a member could suffer bad luck owing to their involvement in an antisocial act. It is their conviction that the supernatural being may withhold their favour, help and benevolence from a person as a result of their sin or disobedience to divine instruction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Failure to be successful in attempts at securing political power could be rationalised as punishment for past wrongdoing in Ayetoro. The community holds the view that the failures of the political class to be deliberate in bringing the dividends of democracy to the citizens of their country is a direct consequence of the sins or disobedience of the nation's citizens. They often teach that until humanity embraces the divine laws their suffering may not be alleviated.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Defeat in battles could be attributed to divine reproof and disapproval arising

from the evil committed by human communities. Defeat in battles both in bible times and in contemporary situations have been linked to disobedience of the human community to divine instructions or mandate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Crop failure or bad weather could be attributed to divine reproof and disapproval arising from the evil committed by human communities. Crop failure or infestation by pests and destructive insects and animals both in bible times and in contemporary situations have been linked to disobedience of the human community to divine instructions or mandate. Ayetoro therefore places serious emphasis on obedience to divine instructions to avert the avalanche of punishments that could result from such acts of disobedience.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Strictly speaking, members of Ayetoro community hardly get involved in disasters in journeys. Members of the community attribute this to a spiritual exercise undertaken by the first monarch who by spiritual means forbade such evils from affecting Ayetoro members. During field work, a young man who proved helpful in the process of data gathering, when asked reasons why he limps on one of his legs replied by saying he was miraculously delivered from death in an auto crash where every other person involved lost their lives. He further revealed that no member of Ayetoro community dies from their involvement in disasters in journeys.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes its manifestation in the form of mild sensory displeasure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes its manifestation in the form of extreme sensory

displeasure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes its manifestation in the form of sickness or illness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes its manifestation in the form of impaired reproduction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes its manifestation in the form of bad luck visited on descendants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that punishment for wrongdoing could come in different forms. This includes failure to have bountiful harvest of fish from the sea

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that supernatural beings bestow rewards on individuals and communities for acting in line with divine instruction

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that the supernatural being bestows rewards. In some instances, they rationalise the reward as being the direct consequence of an identified action or deed of individuals or communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Members of Ayetoro theocratic community belief that the high god rewards the actions and deeds of all mortals. Although they hold the view that the high god need not personally implement the act of apportioning the reward. He could deploy other beings (human or supernatural) to implement the process. However, the decision ultimately rest with the high god while using other beings to carry out the action.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings who implement the process of apportioning rewards for the actions of mortals are held as instruments in the hands of the high god for carrying out the decision of the latter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro community, the supreme high god is conceived as capable of using the impersonal cause-effect principle in giving reward to mortals in accordance with their actions or deeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro community, the supreme high god is conceived as capable of using rewards to encourage religious ritual-devotional adherence from the members. To

show their approval for certain actions, the supreme high god may decide to hand down rewards to encourage religious ritual-devotional adherence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: For the purpose of enforcing group norms, the supreme high god is reputed for his capability to deploy the instrument of rewards as a catalyst for encouraging the kind of behaviours he desires among Ayetoro people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, in an attempt to inhibit selfishness, the supreme high god is reputed to be in the habit of giving tangible rewards to selfless folks so they could become the perfect example for others to follow

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Members of the Ayetoro community do not perceive rewards as randomly given for ambiguous reasons. They hold the view that rewards are usually given to mortals for specific acts or deeds they have carried out.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife. Their belief about rewards is two fold. First, they hold that humans will receive rewards for their actions here in this world and also in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro community, great emphasis is placed on provision for supernatural rewards in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community holds the view that in the afterlife, sensory pleasures would constitute a part of the numerous rewards awaiting those who were faithful in observing group norms while traversing the earth. They believe that they would constantly enjoy magnificent views of mansions, flowing rivers, nourishing fruits and music from well coordinated angelic chorister.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community believes that extreme sensory pleasure are included in the package which her members who be treated to in the afterlife. They agree that the pleasure of ruling over vast territories, exercising dominion over the people and having all of one's desires met are part of the extreme sensory pleasures awaiting the faithful after their transition to the afterlife

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community speaks excitedly of the eternal happiness and joy that will pervade the heart of those admitted into eternal bliss in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not belief that reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not believe that reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro people hold the view that there are several other rewards awaiting those who obeyed community rules and regulations without wavering. For example, the community believes that the needs of those in the blissful afterlife would be met as soon as they have the longing for them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the view that rewards for good deeds begin in this lifetime and continue in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community emphasizes the appropriation of rewards in this life for good deeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, good fortunes are conceived as part of the rewards good people receive in this lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Political success and power in private and public life are held as rewards for the proper conduct of people and groups by the Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro worldview, rewards in the private and public life of people manifest in several forms. According to them, success in personal battles and collective struggles are conceived as reward from the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: Peace and social stability are considered as rewards in this life in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Healthy crops, good catch of aquatic animals in canals, rivers and the Atlantic Ocean and good weather are considered as rewards in this life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, all Ayetoro members experience success and safety in their journeys. Success on journeys is a benefit which accrues to members of the community as a result of their identification with the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Mild sensory pleasure constitute a part of the rewards for living an acceptable life among the Ayetoro population

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Extreme sensory pleasure constitute a part of the rewards for living an acceptable life among the Ayetoro population

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, good health is said to be bestowed on whomsoever the supreme being favours. The favour (good health) they make reference to is a form of reward for the good deeds done in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community holds on to several promises from the bible. They walk in the consciousness that they shall not be barren. Hence reproductive success in the community is seen as a direct derivative of the good deeds of the membership.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The community beliefs that the supreme being's blessings upon them is for them and their children to the fourth generation. As a result, they admit the fact that reward in this life consists of fortune visited on their descendants

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The rewards accruable to anyone who lives right in accordance with Ayetoro standards are too numerous to number. Some of them include promotion in the church hierarchy, higher commitment in community service etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro theocratic community beliefs Jesus Christ is the messiah. According to them, he came into the world more than 2000 years ago to save mankind from the danger of eternal separation from the high god. He is returned to the heavens to prepare a place for them that when they finish their earthly course, they may reign with him (the messiah) and the high god eternally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: Though they claim the messiah's whereabouts is known, the time of his return to take his faithful followers is unknown. They keep striving to follow his instructions while hoping his return will meet them in strict adherence to his teachings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community claim that though their messiah was crucified, he subsequently died but miraculously rose up the third day. He now lives for ever and ever. It is this second (eternal) life which he has that his followers too are promised in the afterlife. The people of Ayetoro do not mistake his identity. They identify his personality and are certain about his attributes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro people claim that their messiah has come and returned to another realm. This is not to say that he is not involved or concerned about their existence or their physical wellbeing. He is actively involved in their daily affairs and superintends over their wellbeing. They hold the belief that he will yet return to take them to his abode at the close of this age.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: Though Ayetoro people believe that their messiah will return in the future, the actual day and time of return is unknown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The common belief in Ayetoro is that their messiah will return in an unspecified time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: The time of the return of Ayetoro's messiah is often spoken of as an event which will happen soon. Although the general belief in the Christian faith is that his return will take place soon, this has not materialised over two millennia. However, they continue to believe in his imminent and quick return.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: The coming of their messiah is two fold. One has taken place already while his return is imminent and would be unannounced.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The messiah's purpose is known according to Ayetoro's theology. They hold that their messiah came to save the world from sin and the oppression of the evil one and they activate these purposes while attempting to appropriate the benefit of his coming to alleviate the suffering of their members in the hands of evil spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro belief that their messiah is a spiritual one. He is not so bothered about political power as he is about spiritual power and authority.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community holds that their messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious tradition and authority.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The Ayetoro community hold that their messiah also came to restore order and peace to the world. According to them, he came to restore hope, displace the evil forces from holding sway over the affairs of humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community beliefs in eschatology. They look up to the end of times in this world and the judgement that would follow the last events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, the belief is held that this world will end. A judgement would follow before a new world will emerge where the good people will reign in a blissful realm. The evil folks however will earn their portion in a lake of fire which shall never be quenched.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: There is another branch of their belief which is to the effect that those who die now will

be in a position of rest until a set time in the future when everyone who has ever lived will be summoned to appear before the judgement seat of the high god. This is where rewards and punishments will be given to those who deserve them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the eschaton believed on in Ayetoro community is one that shall take place in the near future. However, the set date and time is unknown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: The eschaton espoused by Ayetoro community is not one that is set for a distant time in the future. Although it has taken long for this expectation to materialise, they still believe it is for a time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community is clear about their theology relating to eschatology. The time and events surrounding it are well laid out. It is expected at a time in the near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community are not expected to perform any specific tasks to bring about the world's end.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The people of Ayetoro believe in divine judgement. This belief is two fold. They hold that as it pleases the high god, he rewards or punishes the good and bad behaviours of every

member of the human race here and now. This belief serves the purpose of reminding the people of the community that each of their actions shall attract a consequence here on earth. The consequence may be immediate or at some point during their lifetime. Ayetoro's other belief regarding divine judgement stipulates a final judgement which will coincide with the end of this world. This judgement is the final verdict on the actions of all mortals who have lived on earth. The verdict is irreversible and does not have an end date.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Restoration of the world:

– No

Notes: Rather than have the world restored, Ayetoro community belief that a new world will emerge after the expiration of this current one. This current world, according to their belief shall pass away. It shall be burned. After this, another cosmic globe shall emerge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Notes: The new world shall be a new permanent cosmos. It shall be one in which the presence of the supreme being shall be evident. The evil forces which continue to torment this present world shall be completely absent in this new cosmos as the high god himself physically rule and direct its affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro people belief that the political system which shall be operational in the coming world shall be theocratic in nature. The high god himself shall govern its affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: According to the theology of the Ayetoro community, the new world shall have at its core a system of governance which the Christians project and preach.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, those who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Those who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Notes: There are no other survival conditions stipulated by the community. Only those

who are true disciples and followers of the religious ideals projected by the Ayetoro community shall survive the eschaton

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community upholds the norms stipulated in the bible. Some of the norms stipulated in the bible include strict adherence to the ten commandments, obedience to the warnings and instructions of all the prophets sent by the high god with divine messages as recorded in the bible and most importantly, obeying the teachings of Jesus Christ, their messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The moral instructions instituted among the Ayetoro populace are the same with the standards of the bible. There is no conventional versus moral distinction in the religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the centrally important virtues advocated by the Ayetoro group include strict adherence to the ten commandments, obedience to the warnings and instructions of all the prophets sent by the high god with divine messages as recorded in the bible and most importantly, obeying the teachings of Jesus Christ, their messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: The virtues of honesty, trustworthiness and integrity are taught and encouraged among the Ayetoro people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community instils courage, whether in battle in their membership. The community holds the view that many achievements are made possible just by the display of courage and inner strength in battle. Their members are therefore admonished to remain courageous in the face of daunting challenges and battles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community instils courage in their membership. The community holds the view that many achievements are made possible just by the display of courage and inner strength. Their members are therefore admonished to remain courageous at all times

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community teaches her members the importance of compassion, empathy, kindness and benevolence. The leadership of the community keeps the members in constant remembrance of the importance of these virtues. They remind the members that some bible characters exhibited these virtues towards some supernatural beings unknowingly. They were blessed beyond their imaginations as a result of the demonstration such virtues/actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: The community advocates the exhibition of the virtues of mercy, forgiveness and tolerance among their members. They hold that anyone who withholds mercy and forgiveness from others will also not obtain the mercy and forgiveness of the high god. This means so much to them. So, they would do everything possible to stand a chance of obtaining these favours from the supreme being. The community also teaches the importance of being tolerant of others. The members therefore strive to imbibe and demonstrate the practice of these virtues in their daily lives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community teaches her members the importance of generosity and charity. Their members strive to live a life characterised by these virtues always

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness or selfless giving has always been an important virtue in Ayetoro. The community witnessed massive development as a result of the decision to practice communalism. From 1948 till about 1970, the village pulled their human and other personal resources together and submitted their freedom to the sovereignty of the village which channelled the resources as it deemed fit. In the current dispensation of the abolishment of communalism members of the community have continued to demonstrate brotherly love manifested in selflessness as they keep giving of their private possessions to others within and outside the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro admonishes her members to embrace righteousness / moral rectitude in their interactions everyday

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community upholds ritual purity, ritual adherence and abstention from sources of impurity. The community holds the view that strict observance of ritual purity, ritual adherence and abstention from sources of impurity make their prayers receive the quick attention of the supreme being

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community belief in the inculcation of the virtues of respectfulness and courtesy. They teach their members to display them in all their interactions with men and women, young and old.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community teaches that familial obedience is non-negotiable. The community beliefs in filial piety in addition to familial obedience. In their judgement, obedience to the supreme being is often seen not to be in conflict with obedience to parents. However, in the event that the principles of obedience to the supreme being conflicts with obedience to parents, the former must take precedence over the later.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs and teaches the virtues of fidelity and loyalty.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: The community thrives on the cooperation of her members to achieve all the exploits attributed to them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community emphasises the virtues of Independence, creativity and freedom of their members. members are allowed to explore and discover their potentials. They encourage them to be creative and express their freedom to take decisions which affect them individually.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro beliefs in moderation and the frugal use of money and other resources.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: The community beliefs in forbearance, fortitude and patience.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro preaches diligence, self-discipline and excellence. Their mindfulness of these virtues has been a major contributor to their economic and technological advancement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community upholds the principles of assertiveness, decisiveness, confidence, and initiative. These virtues have impacted their development in a lot of ways

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, laziness is considered a terrible vice. Therefore hard work and commitment to labour are virtues which are highly esteemed among the people. Although the community embraced technology and the use of machines in their production lines, the need for members to work hard to achieve community goals has never diminished

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community beliefs that power belongs to the supreme being. The community does not operate a caste system nor segregate on the basis of status or nobility. Some of the monarchs who have reigned in the village have no history of nobility neither do they hail from royal families.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community emphasises the virtues of humility and modesty. The theocratic

settlement embraced humility and modesty in their everyday actions and decisions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro theocratic settlement preaches contentment, serenity and equanimity among her population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Joyfulness, enthusiasm and cheerfulness are virtues which Ayetoro community embraces and teaches within her borders. Her members are encouraged to live with optimism, joy, enthusiasm and remain cheerful despite any challenges they face.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community are taught the importance of optimism and hope in all their endeavours.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Cratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community are taught to always demonstrate gratitude and thankfulness in their daily lives

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches her members to be in reverence, awe and wonder of the almighty whom they daily talk about and popularly claim to serve

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the Ayetoro community are often admonished to exercise faith, belief, trust and the devotion in the supreme being whom they allude to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro leadership admonishes her members to embrace and exhibit wisdom and understanding in all their endeavours. The community holds that wisdom is the principal thing which needs to be pursued and appropriated by all who desire to lead an exceptional life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the view that discernment is a gift which helps proffer solution to difficult and intractable challenges. The level of intelligence which helps citizens understand proper use of resources is also discussed and encouraged by the Ayetoro leadership.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Though beauty and attractiveness are not evil or bad in themselves, Ayetoro community de-emphasises their projection above the real virtues which impact on development and advancement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community projects physical cleanliness and orderliness among their people. A visit to the community reveals the premium placed on cleanliness and orderliness. In a terrain which is naturally not supportive of proper physical planning of housing facilities, Ayetoro unlike other villages around it overcame the natural obstacles created by swamps and the waterlogged terrain to build homes and large boardwalks on stilts which support ease of

movement among other benefits. The tradition of cleanliness in the community is easily seen when the members all participate in the regular sanitation exercise.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The list of virtues advocated and embraced by the Ayetoro theocratic settlement is by no means easily exhaustible. All actions which can be categorised as noble and enviable are encouraged among the people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy is not practiced among people of Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: The family as the basic unit of the society was suppressed during the time when Ayetoro practised communalism. At some point during the industrialisation drive in Ayetoro, marriage was also abolished for a short period. (Barrett, *Two Villages on Stilts*, 1974, p. 4)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Men in Ayetoro are allowed to married multiple women at the same time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro women are only allowed to marry one man at a time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Ideally, Ayetoro bachelors are expected to abstain from sexual activities until marriage. However, in recent times, this is no longer strictly enforced in the community especially when the unmarried bachelor and lady with whom he is involved sexually have plans to contract marriage in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Ideally, Ayetoro spinsters are expected to abstain from sexual activities until marriage. However, in recent times, this is no longer strictly enforced in the community especially when the unmarried spinster and her lover with whom she is involved sexually have plans to contract marriage in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community do not engage in castration

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the community could engage in fasting and praying in order to confront a difficult spiritual situation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: There no taboos on any food item in Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Membership of Ayetoro religious community does not require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Membership of Ayetoro religious community does not require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in Ayetoro religious community does not require sacrifice of adults

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in Ayetoro religious group does not require sacrifice of children

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Membership in Ayetoro religious community does not require self-sacrifice (suicide)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership in Ayetoro religious community does not require sacrifice of property/valuable items

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Membership in Ayetoro religious community requires sacrifice of time for attendance at meetings or services and regular prayers. Although at some point during Ayetoro's industrialisation drive, church meetings were seldom held. This was during the reign of the first Oba (monarch). This however changed during the reign of the second Oba who was concerned about the rejuvenation of Ayetoro's religious life. In recent times, the community has continued to pursue its agenda of spirituality vigorously.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Although life in its entirety is full of risks, humans naturally engage in reasonable risk assessments before deciding on a course of action. Ayetoro community does not encourage blind risks which could bring catastrophic results. Physical risk taking is not encouraged in Ayetoro.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The Ayetoro community follows Christian values and ethics. Members of Ayetoro community are encouraged to keep ethical values like honesty, transparency, truthfulness etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Marginalisation of Ayetoro members by out-group members lasted only a few years after the

founding of the community. This is because Ayetoro was founded by a group of people who opposed certain traditional practices in their homeland. When the community was founded, the local authority in their native land deployed all resources to fight them. They were thus marginalised by out-group members until they attained economic and technological advancement. The situation changed when they became prosperous and were envied by other communities around them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: No mandatory small scale rituals are required of Ayetoro members. However, members are at liberty to engage in small rituals at their convenience

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 2000

Notes: All members of the Ayetoro community are required to attend every regular and special large-scale ritual gathering in the theocratic settlement

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 24

Notes: Ritual gatherings are held in Ayetoro daily

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks performed during ritual performances in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthopraxy checks performed during ritual performances in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: During ritual performances in Ayetoro, synchronic practices are recorded during supplicatory prayers, songs rendition etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are not used in ritual observances in Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community engages in the circumcision of its infant males

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro has no institutionalised food taboos

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro, hairstyles are categorised according to gender. Male members are naturally expected to trim their hair while female members usually keep long hair which could be plaited or styled in acceptable patterns as are allowed in the community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: In Ayetoro community, prayer garments form a part of their religious tradition although they were not part of their religious life when the community was formed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Notes: Ayetoro community does not mandate the use of ornaments for her members. Those willing to use simple ornaments are allowed to do so while others who prefer to be without them are allowed the freedom to continue their worship without them

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Glossolalia is practiced in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Unlike some other African Independent church movements on the African continent, Ayetoro community does not forbid the use of footwear for members clad in prayer garments. Members are allowed to put on their shoes to religious grounds were they may choose to pull them at the door of the meeting place

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Ayetoro community are predominantly from Ilajeland. Each one of them has a natal settlement where they hail from. However, when Ayetoro community was formed, most of the members were disowned by their kith and kin in their natal settlements. This paved the way for them to adopt Ayetoro as their new ancestral home. They thus began to refer to themselves as Ayetoro indigenes. Each one of them thus saw the other as their brother or sister and they related with each other in such manner.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is widespread in Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is widespread and very common in Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Ayetoro community conceives of themselves as a band of saints having a common goal and pursuing a single agenda of continuous service to the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: When Ayetoro practised communalism, the nutritional needs of members was met by the community. However, after communalism was abandoned, the community developed a scheme by which it rises to help members who may be unable to adequately cater for their personal or family needs

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community's famine relief programme is self-operated and handled internally

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Poverty relief for members of the community is not structured in a sophisticated manner.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community handles its poverty relief programme internally. No institutions are organised for the sole aim of carrying out poverty relief in Ayetoro community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: The elders of Ayetoro enjoy a special welfare programme which is an initiative of the current Oba. The current Oba is a grandson of the first monarch of the community. He is seen as a re-incarnation of the first monarch by a section of the membership of the community. His care for the elderly (the remnant of those who migrated to Ayetoro on January 12, 1947 with his late grand father who laboured hard towards Ayetoro's economic and technological advancement) is seen as an attempt to take special care of those who served the community and made it the once popular experiment of a successful theocratic village in Africa.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The care for the elderly in Ayetoro is not available to the group's adherents through an institution

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The community built a primary, secondary and technical school which provided free education to her members before the schools were taken over by the government

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: The religious group runs the schools without the assistance of other separate institutions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: The group's adherents do not interact with other institutional bureaucracy in their social or religious life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide public food storage for members. However, it makes available to members food relief as occasion demands

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No other institution apart from the religious group itself manages the food storage for the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The community does not have the capacity to provide water management, irrigation or flood control in the magnitude that the community needs to survive. Ayetoro is a coastal community located at the tip of the Atlantic Ocean. It is besieged by perennial ocean incursion which has wiped out more

than half of the community's original landscape.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution is currently providing the much needed water management which Ayetoro community currently facing existential threat needs. The national government which is constitutionally saddled with the responsibility of protecting the life and livelihood of her citizens has grossly failed in their responsibility.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Ayetoro community once provided an efficient water transportation scheme which served the coastal communities from Lagos in the west to Cameroon in the east. It boasted of about two dozen large passenger boat which assisted with the movement of persons, goods and services within the region. Ayetoro was a closed community during the period. This meant that her members spent most of their time inside the village. Those who travelled outside the community did so with the consent and permission of the leadership and would have transportation arranged for them by the community. This changed when the community adopted a free economy. The transport system which once operated efficiently has since failed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community does not rely on other institutions for transportation infrastructure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: When the community operated communalism, it did not levy taxes or tithes. In fact, no contributions were taken from members because members did not earn personal income. They contributed their labour to the community and had their needs fully met by the settlement. In recent

times however, there has been a move to encourage members to make contributions to the community church while tithing has recently been introduced. It will take some time to determine the acceptability and success of tithing among the Ayetoro population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government of Nigeria has for a long time levied residents of Ayetoro in the form of taxes. When communalism was in place in the community, there was an arrangement whereby the Oba paid taxes on every adult resident of the community. Since communalism was abolished, the responsibility has fallen on each member to pay their taxes accordingly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The community has an internal control mechanism for crime detection, crime prevention and deterrence. Although the system was better organised under communalism, it has lost much of its grip on the community. The Police has had to assume jurisdiction of security coverage for the settlement in recent times. There is a Police Post located at Idi-Ogba community about 200 meters from Ayetoro. The Police Post provides security for the villages in that axis of Ilajeland.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is done only when necessary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Though the judges provided by the community cannot be said to belong to an institutional order, they still serve the community notwithstanding. They do their best to ensure the sanctity of law and order in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the Nigerian judicial system and have submitted to its authority on several occasions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: The community has not been in the habit of handing capital punishments to their members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Members are not usually sent on exile in Ayetoro. However, there are indications that this has been done in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, members have been given portions of communal area to weed. This is no longer a common practice in the community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: This is not a common practice in Ayetoro

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: This is not usually practiced in Ayetoro community

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

Notes: It is uncertain if any member of the has been executed by the orders of a law court in Nigeria before.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Notes: It is uncertain if any member of the has been sent on exile by the orders of a law court in Nigeria before.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: Notes: It is uncertain if any member of the has been handed corporal punishment by the orders of a law court in Nigeria before.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: While the tussle for the post of the community monarch lasted years back, one of the contenders to the throne was picked up and kept in the custody of the nation's correctional service for months until the government resolved the issue

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Notes: It is uncertain if any member of the has had their property seized by the orders of a law court in Nigeria before.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The group embraces and follows the codes stipulated in the bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to the formal legal codes of Nigeria

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess an institutionalised military.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the community are free to join the Nigerian military if they so wish

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are protected by and subject to the Nigerian military

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The vast majority of the group members belong to the Yoruba ethnic group. The community therefore uses the Yoruba language as their first language and the English language as their second or official language.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Though the Yoruba (a non-religion-specific) language is widely used in the community, it is not an imposition of any institution outside of the religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Though the Yoruba (a non-religion-specific written) language is widely used in the community, it is not an imposition of any institution outside of the religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group follows the Gregorian calendar in determining its activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No formal calendar is provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The community buys the bulk of its food as the Ilaje terrain (a waterlogged landscape) does not support extensive production of food. Most of their protein needs is met through fishing activities in canals, rivers and their engagement in the Atlantic Ocean.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Any food which the community cannot produce is bought in the local markets

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ayetoro, Southwest Nigeria

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Holy Apostles Community, Ayetoro, Barrett, Stanley R.. *The Rise and Fall of an African Utopia: A Wealthy Theocracy in Comparative Perspective*. Waterloo, Ontario, Canada: Wilfrid Laurier University Press, 1977.

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